

Preparation and optical properties of Bi³⁺-doped K₄SrGe₃O₉ as a UVA phosphor

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Abstract: Optical materials with UV emission have diverse applications, for example, in phototherapy, anti-counterfeiting, disinfection, and photocopying. Yet, these materials are mainly activated by rare earth ions with narrow and inflexible emission characteristics. Here, we report on UVA emission from a Bi³⁺-doped K₄SrGe₃O₉ phosphor synthesized by conventional high-temperature solid state reaction at ambient atmosphere. The structure, morphology and luminescent properties of the material were characterized using X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and photoluminescence spectroscopy, demonstrating broadband emission of ultraviolet-A (UVA) light peaking at 353 nm (FWHM ~ 46 nm) when stimulated by ultraviolet radiation at a wavelength of 304 nm. The maximum emission intensity was found for K₄SrGe₃O₉:0.001Bi³⁺, with a quantum yield of 46% and a lifetime of 477 ns.

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1. Introduction

Representing a unique part of the phosphor family, ultraviolet (UV) phosphors, with emission in the ultraviolet-C (UVC, 200-280 nm), ultraviolet-B (UVB, 280-315 nm), and ultraviolet-A (UVA, 315-400 nm), have a range of current and prospective applications, including anti-counterfeiting, disinfection, photocatalysis, imaging, and photodynamic treatment [1–3]. In particular, UVA phosphors have attracted widespread attention in the past two decades because of their potential uses in surface sterilization, drug release and cancer theranostics [4,5]. Yet, designing and synthesizing luminescent materials in the UV range is challenging in view of the available emitter species and host materials.

The development of UV-emitting phosphors depends on two primary factors. First, appropriate emission centers with the capability to emit specific wavelengths in the UV are required, such as Nd³⁺, Tl⁺, Tm³⁺, Eu²⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Gd³⁺, Pb²⁺, and Bi³⁺. Heavy metal species such as Pb²⁺ or Tl⁺ are beyond practical use due to their high toxicity. As the second factor, potential host materials include crystals such as garnets, olivines, catapleiites, melilites, perovskites, parawollastonites, etc. Here, germanates with various crystal structures are of interest. As a prerequisite, the host material must be sufficiently stable against high energy radiation. Furthermore, band gap compatibility condition requires that both the ground state and the excited state of the activator are situated within the host material's band gap [6].

Bi ions have been widely explored due to their flexible emission properties, depending on diverse Bi valence and ligand states [7,8]. Several inorganic material systems doped with Bi³⁺

ions have been reported (e.g., [9–11]). Bismuth-doped germanates have drawn special attention due to the attractive emission wavelength of the $\text{Bi}^{3+} \ ^3\text{P}_{0,1} \rightarrow \ ^1\text{S}_0$ (A-band) transition [12–15].

In the framework of UV emitting phosphors (200–400 nm), roughly 60 different compounds have been identified to date, the majority of which emit in the UVA [16]. Among them, there are currently only a few Bi^{3+} -doped germanate phosphors, i.e., $\text{NaLuGeO}_4:\text{Bi}^{3+}, \text{Eu}^{3+}$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 400$ nm) [17], $\text{LiYGeO}_4:\text{Bi}^{3+}$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 365$ nm) [12,18], $\text{LiScGeO}_4:\text{Bi}^{3+}$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 361$ nm) [5,12,19], $\text{NaGdGeO}_4:\text{Bi}^{3+}, \text{Li}^+$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 400$ nm) [20], $\text{LiLuGeO}_4:\text{Bi}^{3+}$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 350$ nm) [12,21,22], $\text{Mg}_3\text{Y}_2\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_{12}:\text{Bi}^{3+}$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 322$ nm) [23,24], and $\text{BaSc}_2\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_{10}:\text{Bi}^{3+}$ (UVA, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 370$ nm) [25].

Here, we report on $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ (KSGOB) as a phosphor with broad UVA emission. It was synthesized by a conventional solid-state reaction approach in air. The structural, morphological and optical properties are discussed based on complementary characterizations.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials and synthesis

A series of $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0$ mol%) phosphors was successfully synthesized by a solid-state reaction (Fig. S1). The stoichiometric raw materials of K_2CO_3 (98%, Carl Roth GmbH), SrCO_3 (VEB Laborchemie Apolda), GeO_2 (99.999%, Projector GmbH) and Bi_2O_3 (Sofia-Bulgaria) were homogeneously mixed and ground using ethanol in an agate mortar for ~ 20 min. Afterwards, the slurry was placed in the drying oven at 100 °C for 40 min. The dried mixture was reacted in the ambient air atmosphere in an alumina crucible covered with alumina lids at 900 °C for 8 h at a heating rate of 5 °C min^{-1} in a muffle furnace. Then, the samples were cooled to room temperature and pulverized into powder for further use.

2.2. Characterization methods

2.2.1. Microstructural characterization

The phase composition of as-prepared $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ samples was characterized using an X-ray diffractometer (MiniFlex 600, Rigaku) with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54059$ Å) in the 2θ range of 5 – 75° at room temperature. The diffraction data were analyzed using the software Rigaku PDXL (2015) with the PDF2 database.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JEOL JSM-7600 F) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS) was used to analyze the surface morphologies, particle sizes, and elemental distributions of the samples.

2.2.2. Spectroscopic characterizations

X-ray photo-electron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was performed using a Nexxa G2 surface analysis system (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA) with a micro-focus monochromatic X-ray source (Al $\text{K}\alpha$, 1486.6 eV). The binding energy values were calibrated for a $\text{C}1\text{s}$ peak of 284.8 eV.

Diffuse reflection spectra (DRS) referenced to a reflection standard (Spectralon) were recorded over the spectral range of 250–800 nm using a double-beam UV-vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Cary 5000, Agilent Technologies, USA) equipped with Praying Mantis (Harrick, USA) accessory.

Photoluminescence emission (PL) and photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra were collected using a high-resolution spectrofluorometer (Fluorolog-3, Horiba) equipped with photomultiplier tubes (Hamamatsu R928, R928P, Shimokanzo, Japan), and a 450 W Xe lamp as the excitation source. Time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) using pulsed laser diodes at excitation wavelengths of 309 nm was used to record the luminescence decay curves at room temperature (RT) on the same device. The photoluminescence quantum yield (QY) measurements

under 304 nm excitation wavelength were determined employing a Horiba Quanta-phi external integrating sphere accessory, which was connected to the same spectrofluorometer by optical fibers.

To visualize emission from the samples, a UV lamp (Konrad Benda, Typ NU-4 KL, KW 254 nm and LW 366 nm, 220 Volt, 2 × 4 Watt, 0.18 Amp., Wiesloch, Germany) was used. All photographic images were recorded with a digital camera.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The structure drawings were generated using the free VESTA (ver. 3.5.8) software. For SEM images, ImageJ software (version 1.45d; National Institute of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA) as the image processing software was utilized. The XPS peaks were fitted using XPSPEAK41 software, using a linear-type background subtraction followed by Gaussian-Lorentzian peak fitting. The UV lamp in graphical abstract is created with BioRender.com.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Crystal structure, phase and morphology analysis

XRD patterns of as-prepared $K_4Sr_{1-x}Ge_3O_9:xBi^{3+}$ samples ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0$ and 6.0 mol%) at room temperature are shown in Fig. 1. All samples exhibit single phase composition when x is lower than 5.0 and their XRD patterns match the standard profile of $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ (PDF#01-083-1342). A secondary phase ($Bi_{0.75}Sr_{0.25}O_{1.37}$) emerges, when x is higher than 5.0, which indicates that the $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ lattice is unable to accommodate the Bi^{3+} ions at such high concentration. Moreover, with further examination, it becomes evident that there is an irregular displacement of the main diffraction peak at $2\theta = 30.39^\circ$ when Bi^{3+} replacing other ions in the host lattice. The reason for this irregularity is not clear yet and requires further investigation.

The schematic crystal structure of $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ is presented in Fig. 2(a). It belongs to the space group ($Pa\bar{3}-T_h^6$) cubic phase with a lattice constant $a = 16.625(1)$ Å. The structure of $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ consists of isolated puckered twelve-membered rings built up by $[GeO_4]$ tetrahedra (Fig. 2(b)), in contrast to the fact that only three-, four-, six-, eight-, and nine-membered rings have been confirmed in cyclosilicates and germanates. There are five distinct types of K sites denoted as K(1), K(2), K(3), K(4), and K(5) (Fig. S2(a)). Additionally, there are two categories of Sr and Ge sites, donated as Sr(1), Sr(2), Ge(1), and Ge(2), respectively (Fig. S2(b-c)). There are also six different types of O sites, labeled as O(1), O(2), O(3), O(4), O(5), and O(6). Each host cell unit consists of basic units of $[K(1)O_6]$, $[K(2)O_6]$, $[K(3)O_6]$, $[K(5)O_6]$, $[K(4)O_5]$ and $[Sr(1)O_6]$, $[Sr(2)O_6]$ octahedra and $[Ge(1)O_4]$, $[Ge(2)O_4]$ tetrahedra. Both the potassium and the strontium atoms are consistently six-coordinated, with the exception of K(4), for which sixfold coordination can only be achieved by including the somewhat longer K – O distance of 3.28 Å [26]. From the Shannon ion radius table [27], it can be shown that the Bi^{3+} ion ($r = 1.03$ Å, CN = 6) has a lower radius compared to the Sr^{2+} ion ($r = 1.18$ Å, CN = 6). The K^+ ion ($r = 1.38$ Å, CN = 6) exhibits a much greater radius in comparison to the Bi^{3+} ion. Therefore, the incorporation of Bi^{3+} ions into the matrix may happen by the substitution of Sr^{2+} ions. This was established by calculating the difference in ion radius (in percentage terms) between the doping center (Bi^{3+}) and the replaced ions (K^+ , Sr^{2+}) based on Hume–Rothery rules [28];

$$D_r = 100\% \times \frac{[|R_m(CN) - R_d(CN)|]}{R_m(CN)} \quad (1)$$

where the D_r , CN, $R_m(CN)$, $R_d(CN)$ variables in the Eqn. (1) represent the percentage difference in ionic radius, the coordination number, the ionic radius of the host cation, and the doped ion, respectively. The determined D_r value of K^+ and Sr^{2+} were 25% and 13%, for K^+ exceeding

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of $K_4Sr_{1-x}Ge_3O_9:xBi^{3+}$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0$ and 6.0 mol%) samples and the standard card of $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ (PDF#01-083-1342) and enlarged XRD patterns in 2θ range of $30.3\text{--}30.6^\circ$.

the acceptable difference (15%) for good solubility. A higher electronegativity values of Sr^{2+} supports the substitution of Sr^{2+} by Bi^{3+} . Therefore, it can be expected that Bi^{3+} ions have a higher tendency to substitute Sr^{2+} ions.

SEM images of the $K_4Sr_{0.999}Ge_3O_9:0.001Bi^{3+}$ sample are shown in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. S3(a-d). A large amount of irregularly shaped and agglomerated particles was confirmed in the sample. The EDS mapping of the sample shows that the main host elements such as K, Sr, Ge, and O, as well as Bi dopant are uniformly dispersed throughout the sample without any evidence of element segregation or phase separation (Fig. 3(b-g)). The calculated and theoretical amounts of each element are almost identical (inset of Fig. 3(g) and Table S1).

3.2. Valence state analysis of Bi ions

The alteration of the host material enables the observation of many bismuth valence states, each of which has a significant influence on the photoluminescent properties. Consequently, it is essential to first ascertain the valence state of the doped materials. A representative XPS spectrum of the $K_4Sr_{0.99}Ge_3O_9:0.01Bi$ is shown in Fig. 4(a). Two peaks at around 164 and 159 eV can be detected (Fig. 4(b)). The Bi 4f signal shapes and binding energies are in good agreement with the $4f_{5/2}$ and $4f_{7/2}$ spin-orbit splitting of the Bi^{3+} ion, respectively. It is important to point out that the deconvoluted peaks at 158.60 eV ($4f_{7/2}$) and 164.12 eV ($4f_{5/2}$) can be assigned to the trivalent Bi^{3+} [29–32].

Based on the idea of ionic radius similarity, the Bi^{3+} ion is found to occupy the Sr^{2+} ion lattice, resulting in a charge mismatch issue that necessitates charge compensation. Hence, the presence of charge defects is a possibility. These may be generated by the creation of a Sr^{2+} vacancy in

Fig. 2. (a) Crystal structure of $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ observed along the standard orientation. (b) Projection of the isolated puckered twelve-membered rings constructed by $Ge(1)O_4$ and $Ge(2)O_4$ tetrahedra.

close proximity to two Bi^{3+} ions, or a K^+ vacancy in close proximity to one Bi^{3+} ion. Then, charge balance is facilitated by the presence of additional O^{2-} ions, which have the potential to be absorbed by the host material during the calcination process in air. Oxygen vacancy defects are easily formed in the multi-element oxide matrix as a result of high-temperature treatment. A Gaussian fit of the XPS O 1s orbital signal reveals the presence of distinct binding energy values, indicating the occurrence of adsorbed oxygen [33–36]. The XPS spectra shown in Fig. S5 offer evidence supporting the assertion that the sample exhibits limited chemical stability when exposed to atmospheric conditions, as well as a propensity for moisture absorption from the surrounding environment.

3.3. Photoluminescence properties of $K_4Sr_{1-x}Ge_3O_9:xBi^{3+}$ phosphor

The optical absorption properties of $KSGO:xBi^{3+}$ ($0.0\% \leq x \leq 6.0\%$) were investigated by analyzing the diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) (see Fig. 5(a)). It exhibits significant reflectivity within the wavelength range of 400 to 800 nanometers. With the addition of Bi^{3+} ions, a distinct absorption peak at around 300 nm becomes apparent. This overlapped peak corresponds to the transitions from the 1S_0 state to the 1P_1 and 3P_1 states of Bi^{3+} . The Kubelka-Munk function and the Tauc relation were used to calculate the optical bandgap [37]:

$$F(R_\infty) = \frac{\alpha}{S} = (1 - R_\infty)^2 / 2R_\infty \quad (2)$$

$$(F(R_\infty)h\nu)^{1/n} = k(h\nu - E_g) \quad (3)$$

where $F(R_\infty)$, R_∞ , α , and S represent the Kubelka-Munk function, $R_\infty = R_{\text{sample}}/R_{\text{standard}}$ diffuse reflection ratio, the absorption, and the scattering coefficient, respectively. The other symbols including h , ν , $h\nu$, k , E_g and n represent the Planck constant, frequency, photon energy, proportionality constant, optical band gap value and a transition coefficient (1/2 direct allowed transition, 2 indirect allowed transition), respectively.

The result shows a decrease in the bandgap from 5.39 eV in KSGO to 4.25 eV when $n = 1/2$ in $KSGO:0.1Bi^{3+}$ as shown in Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 5(d).

Fig. 3. (a) SEM image of the representative $K_4SrGe_3O_9$ particle (0.1 mol% Bi^{3+}) at magnification of 250, (b–f) The EDS elemental distribution mapping of K (b), Sr (c), Ge (d), O (e), and Bi (f), confirming the uniform distribution of the elements in the sample. (g) The EDS pattern analysis on the selected area of the sample and the inset shows the comparison of the theoretical and calculated values of the elements in the atomic percentage (at.%).

Fig. 4. (a) The XPS spectrum of the $K_4Sr_{0.99}Ge_3O_9:0.01Bi^{3+}$ sample, (b) high resolution Bi 4f XPS spectrum of the same compound.

Fig. 5. (a) The diffuse reflectance spectra of KSGO and (c) KSGO: xBi^{3+} ($0.0\% \leq x \leq 6.0\%$) and the PLE spectra of KSGO:0.1 Bi^{3+} ($\lambda_{em} = 354$ nm). The functional curve of $(F(R)hv)^2$ and hv for calculation of the E_g value at (b) $x=0.0$ (d) $x=0.1$, respectively.

The PLE and PL spectra measured at room temperature (Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b)), were utilized to investigate the optical characteristics of $K_4Sr_{1-x}Ge_3O_9:xBi^{3+}$. To get a more comprehensive understanding, the photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra of $K_4Sr_{0.98}Ge_3O_9:0.02Bi^{3+}$ monitored at 353 nm emission were well deconvoluted into two Gaussian profiles. These two overlapped broad bands profiles centered at about 34381 cm^{-1} (290 nm) and 31840 cm^{-1} (314 nm), which can be attributed to Jahn-Teller split $^1S_0 \rightarrow ^3P_1$ transition; Jahn-Teller splitting of the $Bi^{3+} \ ^3P_1$ excited state in two distinct Sr^{2+} sites that are occupied by Bi^{3+} ions (referred to as Bi(1) and Bi(2)) in structure [4,38]. The Fig. 6(b) illustrates the photoluminescence spectra of $K_4Sr_{1-x}Ge_3O_9:xBi^{3+}$ samples with varying concentrations of Bi^{3+} dopants, when excited at a wavelength of 304 nm. The emission spectrum of different concentrations of Bi^{3+} gives an analogous broad band ranging from 320 nm to 450 nm with the highest intensity peaked at 353 nm for $x = 0.1\text{ mol}\%$ which is attributed to the $^3P_1 \rightarrow ^1S_0$ transition of Bi^{3+} ions [39–42]. Additionally, an analogous emission peak of the host that occurs at around 353 nm with very low intensity was observed (see Fig. S6).

The emission intensity of the KSGO: xBi^{3+} ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0$ and $6.0\text{ mol}\%$) phosphors for the peaks at 353 nm exhibit a gradual decrease with increasing Bi^{3+} concentration. The optimal concentration for the strongest intensity is observed at $x = 0.1\text{ mol}\%$ with a FWHM of 46 nm (see Fig. 6(c) and Fig. 6(d)). PL peak also shows a consecutive gradual redshift with introducing Bi^{3+} ions (Fig. 6(e)). The decrease in luminescence intensity of KSGO: xBi^{3+} above $x = 0.1\text{ mol}\%$ is attributed to the concentration quenching effect. An increase in the concentration of Bi^{3+} ions leads to a decrease in the distance between these ions, promoting nonradiative transitions and subsequently causing a reduction in the intensity of luminescence. In order to better understand the process of quenching, the Blasse equation was used to determine the critical distance (R_c) [43]:

$$R_c \approx 2 \left(\frac{3V}{4\pi x_c N} \right)^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

where R_c represents the critical distance, V is the volume of the unit cell, x_c refers to the optimal or critical concentration of dopant ions that results in quenching, and N is the quantity of available sites for the dopant inside the unit cell. Based on the given values of $V = 4594.994141\text{ \AA}^3$, $N = 16$, and $x_c = 0.001$, the critical distance R_c is calculated to be around 82 \AA , which exceeds the distance of exchange interaction ($\sim 5\text{ \AA}$). Hence, it is inferred that the quenching of Bi^{3+} ions occurs due to multipolar interaction according to the report of Dexter and Van Uitert [44].

In order to conduct a more in-depth examination of the multipolar interaction, it is possible to evaluate the probable mechanism of multipolar energy transfer using the equation put forward by Van Uitert [44]:

$$\frac{I}{x} = [(1 + \beta(x)^{\theta/3})]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where the variables x and I denote the concentration of the activator ion and its related emission intensity, respectively. The symbol β denotes a constant that is specific to a particular host lattice and the circumstances of excitation. The value of θ may be either 6, 8, or 10, representing the dipole–dipole (d–d), dipole–quadrupole (d–q), and quadrupole–quadrupole (q–q) interactions, respectively. Figure 7 shows the most accurate linear correlation between the $\log(I/x)$ and the $\log(x)$, with a slope of $-\theta/3 = -1.518$. Consequently, the value of θ is calculated to be 4.554, which is close to 6. As a result, the energy transfer mechanism is attributed to the d–d interaction [45,46]. Fig. S4 displays the Commission Internationale de L’Eclairage (CIE) chromaticity coordinates ($x = 0.15611$, $y = 0.0697$) of $K_4Sr_{0.999}Ge_3O_9:0.1\text{ mol}\%Bi^{3+}$ sample stimulated by 304 nm radiation. Table 1 provides an overview of the most common phosphor materials activated by Bi^{3+} ions, and it also includes a comparison of their luminous properties with the as-synthesized KSGOB samples. Most phosphor materials doped by Bi^{3+} ions display a broad-spectrum emission, whereas there are just a few phosphor hosts that emit in the UVA range.

Fig. 6. (a) PLE spectra of $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 \text{ mol\%}$) monitored at 353 nm and PLE deconvolution of the $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{0.98}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:0.02\text{Bi}^{3+}$ phosphor, (b) PL spectra of $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 \text{ mol\%}$) under 304 nm light excitation (the inset shows digital photos of $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{0.999}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:0.001\text{Bi}^{3+}$ under irradiation by the UV lamp at 254 nm), (c) The peak at the maximum intensity with certain 2θ for different Bi³⁺ concentrations in the UV region, (d) Comparison of the integral intensity for different Bi³⁺ concentrations in the UV region, (e) Normalized photoluminescence spectra of $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9$ at different Bi³⁺ concentrations, (f) The internal quantum yields of $\text{K}_4\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9: x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 \text{ mol\%}$) phosphors for the peak at UV region.

Table 1. An overview of Bi-activated based on germanate polycrystals (SSR: Solid State Reaction, UVA: Ultraviolet-Type A, Vis: Visible, NIR: Near-Infrared, and -: Not reported).

Phosphors	Synthesis, atmosphere	Excitation peak/band [nm]	Emission peak/band [nm]	λ_{em} at	FWHM (nm)	Quantum Efficiency (QE)			Ref.
						Absorption (%)	Internal (%)	External (%)	
CaZnGe ₂ O ₆ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	251	468	Vis	–	–	–	–	[47]
BaZnGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	312	440, 595	Vis	–	–	–	–	[48]
KGaGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	240, 320	420, 495	Vis	–	–	–	–	[49]
NaYGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	298	402	Vis	–	–	–	–	[50]
NaLuGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	254	400	UVA	–	–	–	–	[51]
NaLuGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺ , Eu ³⁺	SSR, air	316	400	UVA	–	–	–	–	[17]
NaGdGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺ , Li ⁺	SSR, air	310	400	UVA	–	–	–	–	[20]
LiYGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	254	350	UVA	–	–	–	–	[18]
LiLuGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺ , Yb ³⁺	SSR, air	254, 310	350	UVA	–	–	–	–	[21]
LiScGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	280	365	UVA	–	–	–	–	[5,19]
Sr ₃ Y ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	275	374, 465, 730	UVA-Vis, NIR	–	–	–	–	[52]
Zn ₂ GeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	300	455, 515	Vis	–	–	–	–	[7]
Lu ₂ CaGeO ₆ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	240–340	420	Vis	–	–	–	–	[53]
BaSc ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₀ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	305	370	UVA	–	–	81.0	49.32	[25]
Mg ₃ Y ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	290	322	UVA	35	–	63.89	–	[23]
K ₂ MgGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	335	614	Vis	48	–	66.6	–	[54]
Ca ₃ Lu ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	380	476	Vis	47	57	52	30	[46]
Sr ₃ Lu ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	390	466	Vis	40	–	57	–	[55]
Ba ₂ ZnGe ₂ O ₇ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	346	500	Vis	129–116	–	70–85	–	[56]
La ₄ GeO ₈ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	397	600	Vis	103	–	88	69	[57]
K ₄ CaGe ₃ O ₉ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	320	400	UVA	43	–	61.13	–	[36]
Ba ₅ GeO ₄ Br ₆ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	315	491	Vis	138	–	27.3	–	[58]
Sr ₃ Sc ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	289, 386	333, 487	UVA-Vis	53	–	–	–	[59]
Ca ₄ ZrGe ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	370	437	Vis	–	–	88.1	–	[60]
Sr ₃ Ga ₂ Ge ₄ O ₁₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	394	461	Vis	–	–	–	–	[61]
Ca ₂ LuZrScAl ₂ GeO ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	290; 365	330, 467; 467	UVA-Vis	34; 69	–	72; 60	–	[62]
CsAlGe ₂ O ₆ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	330	535	Vis	165	–	66.73	–	[63]
La ₂ MgGeO ₆ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	319 240, 300	400 400	UVA	–	–	–	–	[64]; [65]
BaGeO ₃ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	312	466	Vis	142.9651	–	–	–	[66]
Sr ₃ La ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	380	400	UVA	–	–	–	–	[67]
Y ₂ GeO ₅ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	260, 300	369	UVA	–	–	–	–	[68]
Ba ₂ Ga ₂ GeO ₇ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	365; 300, 387	497; 497, 611	Vis	–	–	–	–	[69]
Lu ₂ Ge ₂ O ₇ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	290	335	UVA	–	–	–	–	[70]
Lu ₂ GeO ₅ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	265	370	UVA	–	–	–	–	[71]
La ₃ Ga ₅ GeO ₁₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	255	440	Vis	–	–	–	–	[72]
Ca ₃ Ga ₂ Ge ₃ O ₁₂ :Bi	SSR, air	287; 455	305; 750	Vis; NIR	–; 102	–	–	–	[73]
CaMgGeO ₄ :Bi ³⁺	SSR, air	316	346	UVA	–	–	–	–	[74]

Fig. 7. Dependency and the best fitting linear relationship between $\log(I/x)$ and $\log(x)$ for KSGO: $x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ phosphors.

The internal quantum yields (QY) of KSGO: $x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0,$ and 6.0 mol%) phosphors (Fig. 6(f) and Table 2), provide further confirmation of the optimal Bi^{3+} concentration.

Table 2. Quantum yield (QY) for each sample at room temperature.

Bi^{3+} (x mol%)	QY (%) at 353 nm
0.1	45.9
0.5	44.3
1.0	25.4
2.0	17.3
3.0	9.0
4.0	6.6
5.0	6.1
6.0	5.1

Figure 8(a-b) shows the luminescence decay lifetimes of all Bi^{3+} ions doped materials at room temperature ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 309$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 353$ nm). The following double exponential formula provides a perfect fit to their decay curves [75,76]:

$$I(t) = I_0 + A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_1}\right) + A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_2}\right) \quad (6)$$

In the given equation, $I(t)$ represents the luminescence intensity, A_1 and A_2 are constants, t denotes the time, and τ_1 and τ_2 correspond to the short decay and long decay components, respectively. Furthermore, it is possible to calculate the average lifetime (τ_{ave}) as follows [75,76]:

$$\tau_{\text{ave}} = \frac{A_1 \tau_1^2 + A_2 \tau_2^2}{A_1 \tau_1 + A_2 \tau_2} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 8. (a) Luminescence decay lifetimes of $\text{K}_2\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_3\text{O}_9:\text{xBi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0$ mol%) under $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 309$ nm for the peaks at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 353$ nm, (b) Comparison of the luminescence average lifetimes at 353 nm for different concentration of Bi^{3+} .

The fluorescence average lifetimes for the emission peak monitored at 353 nm for different concentrations of Bi^{3+} ions in the host (0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, and 6.0 mol%) were calculated to be 477 ns, 504 ns, 412 ns, 378 ns, 361 ns, 355 ns, 365 ns, and 403 ns, respectively. The fitting parameters for all studied samples are summarized in Table S2 (Supplement 1). It is evident that all of them are in the nano-second range, aligning with the normal behavior seen in Bi^{3+} -activated phosphors inside an octahedral crystal field and the maximum τ value belongs to the sample with 0.5 mol% of Bi^{3+} ions. The short decay components, found around 20 ns (see Table S2), can be probably associated with interaction (energy transfer) between the Bi^{3+} ions and defect sites generated in host matrix, while long decay components (~ 400 ns) can be attributed to luminescence decay within Bi^{3+} ions.

For the host, the experimental data exhibits a strong correlation with the three-exponential decay curve and the average decay time were calculated by using the equations provided in Supplement 1 Note S1. The calculated average lifetime is 11 ns.

Figure 9 depicts the PL mechanism, which can be inferred from the data presented above. The energy levels of Bi^{3+} consisted of the ground state $^1\text{S}_0$ and three triplets, namely $^3\text{P}_0$, $^3\text{P}_1$, and $^3\text{P}_2$, as well as one singlet ($^1\text{P}_1$) excited states. The electron transitions from the ground state ($^1\text{S}_0$) to the excited states ($^3\text{P}_0$ and $^3\text{P}_2$) are considered spin-forbidden and crystal field-forbidden transitions, as dictated by the selection rule. Hence, the two overlapped excitation bands seen in $\text{KSGO}:\text{xBi}^{3+}$ may be attributed to the electron transitions occurring from the ground state $^1\text{S}_0$ to the excited states $^3\text{P}_1$. The $^1\text{P}_1$ excited electrons transfer to the $^3\text{P}_1$ energy level by a nonradioactive transition and accompanied by the excited electrons at the $^3\text{P}_1$ energy level return to the ground state by the emission of UVA radiation.

Fig. 9. Schematic representation of the proposed UVA PL mechanism in KSGO: $x\text{Bi}^{3+}$ ($x = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0$ mol%) phosphor.

4. Conclusions

This study offers a series of Bi^{3+} -doped $\text{K}_4\text{SrGe}_3\text{O}_9$ UVA phosphors. Their investigation was conducted systematically with respect to crystal structure, essential photoluminescence (PL) and photoluminescence excitation (PLE) behavior, quantum yields (QY), emission lifetime, and the underlying photoluminescence mechanism. The results from XRD and SEM-EDS-mapping analysis demonstrated that the introduction of Bi^{3+} as a dopant did not result in any substantial alterations of the crystal structure and morphology up to a critical dopant concentration. According to the Tauc plot, band gaps for undoped and doped germanate were 5.39 eV and 4.25 eV, respectively. By introducing the Bi^{3+} activator, the analysis of the PL spectrum and of the associated decay curve revealed that the phosphor KSGOB exhibits a broadband UVA emission (FWHM ~ 46 nm) centered at 353 nm. The emission characteristics are attributed to the transition of Bi^{3+} ions from the $^3\text{P}_1$ state to the $^1\text{S}_0$ state with an optimal quantum yield of 46%. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) provided evidence on the presence of Bi^{3+} ions within the host lattice when exposed to ambient air conditions. The prepared phosphors show a potential application in anticounterfeiting, sterilization, phototherapy, as well as pc-UV-LEDs applications.

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Data availability. Data will be made available on request.

Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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